

Development of a Nozzle Concept for In Situ Foaming in the Material Extrusion Process

Motivation

Ex situ foaming

Figure modified from [1]

- Time consuming downstream process steps required
- Foaming degree within component cannot be varied

In situ foaming

Figure modified from [1]

- Time consuming upstream process steps required
- In case of PBA: Degree of foaming depends on time

[1] Sun B and Wu L (2022), Research progress of 3D printing combined with thermoplastic foaming.

Motivation

Novel foaming process

Final nozzle concept

Base nozzle

4 mm

Porous material (PM)

4 mm

[2]

Modular nozzle

4 mm

[2] <https://amespore.com/de/product/amespore-b-scheibenfilter-aus-bronze/>

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Polymer Infiltration into Porous Materials

Schematic test setup for infiltration testing

Effect of process parameters on foam structure

Study Setup:

- Hollow cylinder inside nozzle: PM-316L-17-0,1
- Varied:
 - Gas pressure p_G
 - Nozzle temperature T_N
 - Feed rate v

Conditions:

- $T_N \times p_G$ grid
- Each tested at
 - $v = 0,5 \frac{mm}{s}$
 - $v = 2,0 \frac{mm}{s}$
 - $v = 3,5 \frac{mm}{s}$

→ 27 parameter combinations

Effect of process parameters on foam structure

$$v = 0,5 \text{ mm/s}$$

Effect of process parameters on foam structure

p_M can be idealized as steady, laminar flow through a cylindrical pipe:

$$p_M = \frac{128L}{\pi d^4} Q_M \cdot \eta \rightarrow p_M \propto Q_M \cdot \eta$$

Effect of process parameters on foam structure

Summary and Outlook

+ Adjustable porosity

+ Foaming degree not time-dependent

+ Nozzle can be integrated into existing MEX systems

Thank you for listening!